

DIFFIE-HELLMAN KEY EXCHANGE (DH), AES, AND SHA FOR DATA INTEGRITY IN SECURE COMMUNICATION

¹ N. DHARANI, PG STUDENT IN DEPT OF CSE IN SREE VAHINI INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, TIRUVURU, A.P, 521235.

² Dr. K.V. PANDURANGARAO Ph. D, HOD & PROFESSOR IN DEPT OF CSE IN SREE VAHINI INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, TIRUVURU, A.P, 521235.

³ D.JYOTHI , M.Tech , ASSISTANT PROFESSOR IN DEPT OF CSE IN SREE VAHINI INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, TIRUVURU, A.P, 521235.

Abstract:

Safe communication necessitates maintaining data integrity, confidentiality, and authenticity. This paper presents an integrated approach to achieve strong security by combining the AES, Secure Hash Algorithm SHA, and Diffie-Hellman key exchange. The Diffie-Hellman protocol makes it possible for two parties to exchange secure keys over an unstable channel, allowing them to create a shared secret key that is used for symmetric encryption. Data confidentiality is ensured by the symmetric key encryption algorithm AES's strong encryption capabilities and efficient operation. Additionally, the SHA ensures data integrity by producing a unique hash value for every input, thereby facilitating the verification of data authenticity and integrity.

Sensitive data can be protected during transmission with a complete security solution provided by the integration of these cryptographic techniques. This paper examines the roles and interactions of Diffie-Hellman, AES, and SHA in creating a secure communication framework, as well as the theoretical underpinnings, real-world applications, and security considerations of doing so. By means of this combination, we present improved security protocols that tackle the issues of contemporary data transfer and communication security.

Key Words: AES, SHA, Data Integrity, DH

Introduction

Information transmission security is more important than ever in a time when digital communication is widely used. Advanced cryptographic techniques have greatly strengthened the security framework that is required to prevent unauthorized access and tampering with sensitive data. In order to create a secure communication system that guarantees data confidentiality, integrity, and authenticity, This paper introduces a comprehensive security methodology that integrates the Diffie-Hellman key exchange protocol, AES, and SHA. The Diffie-Hellman key exchange protocol, developed in 1976 by Whitfield Diffie and Martin Hellman, allowed two parties to securely exchange a cryptographic key over an unpredictable channel, revolutionizing the field of cryptography. This shared secret key is necessary for symmetric encryption, which uses the same key for both message encryption and decryption to prevent hackers from accessing transmitted data.

Although data confidentiality is safeguarded by encryption, data integrity and authenticity must also be guaranteed. The Secure Hash Algorithm (SHA) comes in very handy in this situation. With variable input data, SHA functions—SHA-256 and SHA-3 in particular—produce a fixed-size hash value, guaranteeing that even the smallest change in the input produces a noticeably different hash output. To ensure that data hasn't been altered during transmission, this feature is crucial.

A complete security solution can be achieved by combining these three cryptographic techniques: AES provides robust data encryption, Diffie-Hellman ensures secure key exchange, and SHA verifies data integrity. This integration addresses the three primary concerns of contemporary communication security: protection against unauthorized access, data integrity, and authentication verification.

The need for secure communication is greater than ever in the current digital era. Data is vulnerable to interception, tampering, and unauthorized access as it travels over different networks. Protecting sensitive information and upholding confidence in digital communications depend heavily on data confidentiality, integrity, and authenticity. This paper presents a comprehensive approach using the three essential cryptographic techniques: Diffie-Hellman key exchange, AES, and Secure Hash Algorithm SHA. Every one of these methods is essential for protecting data while it is being transmitted. Diffie-Hellman Key Distribution: Using an unsecure channel, this protocol enables two parties to safely generate a shared secret key. Diffie-Hellman makes sure that even if an attacker intercepts the exchanged messages, they are unable to determine the shared key by taking advantage of the mathematical characteristics of discrete logarithms. The basis for safe communication is then established by using this key for symmetric encryption. Standard for AES After establishing the shared key, the data is encrypted using the widely used symmetric encryption algorithm AES. Because of its solid security and high performance, AES is a good choice for effectively encrypting big volumes of data. We guarantee that the data stays private and is only accessible to the designated parties by utilizing AES. Hash Algorithm Secure (SHA): SHA is used to create a distinct hash value for every message in order to preserve data integrity and authenticity. By serving as a digital fingerprint, this hash value enables recipients to confirm that the data was not changed during transmission. The data is deemed undamaged if the calculated hash value agrees with the one sent with the message; if not, it suggests possible manipulation. As shown below figure simple model Diffie-Hellman key exchange architecture.

Figure 1: Proposed Key Generation Architecture.

2. Literature Survey:

In the industrial domains of the future, components must possess interconnectedness. Numerous new paradigms, such as Industry 4.0, Internet of Things, autonomous driving, and cyber physical systems, depend on inter connection. While interconnectedness is essential for meeting future requirements, it also raises the risk of system attacks and can allow unauthorized access to systems. Systems of the future will be made up of many interconnected components. The requirements for these components vary (i.e., security, real-time, availability). It is especially important to maintain control over information sharing and communication with vital constituents. This paper is about safe one-way communication between components with different levels of criticality on the same hardware [1].

Several methods were applied to enhance and suggest elliptic curve-based cryptography systems. In particular, the Diffie-Hellman key exchange protocol is the main component of most of these systems. In this work, we present an efficient approach based on block matrices integrated with elliptic curves to enhance the security of this protocol. With the new system, we can reduce the elliptic curve without increasing the key size. Therefore, depending on the block matrices chosen, the proposed protocol security will be harder to solve than the original protocol because it must solve the Elliptic Curve Discrete Logarithm Problem more than once [2].

Security is of utmost importance in data handling, communication, message transmission, and electronic transactions on public networks. Cryptography, or secret writing, is the process of transforming messages through encryption to make data safe from attack. The symmetric encryption standard AES is advised by NIST. It has been demonstrated that AES is a very fast,

secure, and robust encryption algorithm. AES is widely used due to its excellent proficiency and ease of use. But since cyber attacks have changed recently, security professionals must continue to work hard in the lab developing fresh tactics to foil attackers. Brute-force, differential, algebraic, and linear attacks are examples of possible attacks on symmetric algorithms [3].

The quick development of technology and the spread of smart devices has made connecting to the internet more difficult in many ways. Some of these challenges include maintaining communication security and protecting user credentials. These days, the two main issues in any complex networked communications ecosystem are data integrity and user privacy. Hashing functions are widely used in cryptography to guarantee data integrity in untrusted environments. Identity verification and non-repudiation services are additionally rendered through the use of digital signatures and hash functions. The federal National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) created the SHA with the intention of delivering security and long-term peak performance. The SHA-1, SHA-2, and SHA-3 hashing standards are the most widely used ones. This essay begins with discussing the history of hashing before going into detail about how the SHA family came to be.

. Comparing different hashing standards and highlighting their security capabilities, efficacy, and susceptibilities to frequent attacks is the primary objective.

Statistical analysis, performance analysis, and thorough fault analysis were used throughout the entire assessment process within a predetermined test environment. The study's conclusions highlight SHA-1's shortcomings and evaluate the security advantages of all the widely used SHA-2 and SHA-3 variants. The study also shows that SHA-3 is the most cost-effective way to reduce inexperienced hackers and enable better performance [4].

The DH key exchange algorithm, which provides a secure method of exchanging cryptographic keys over an unreliable channel, is the foundation of modern cryptographic protocols. Its susceptibility to Man-in-the-Middle (MitM) attacks, however, poses a serious problem. In this review, we examined several strategies and enhancements aimed at thwarting MitM attacks against the DH key exchange algorithm. In conclusion, preventing MitM attacks on the DH key exchange requires a multifaceted approach that incorporates PKI, ECC, authentication techniques, and ongoing vigilance with regard to security protocols. The Diffie-Hellman key exchange algorithm, which provides a secure method of exchanging cryptographic keys over an unreliable channel, is the foundation of modern cryptographic protocols. By combining these techniques, we can significantly increase the security of the DH key exchange while simultaneously ensuring the confidentiality and integrity of secure communications in a world growing more interconnected by the day. The importance of cryptographic protocols' constant innovation and adaptation is emphasized in this review as a means of preventing potential threats and maintaining robust security in digital communications [5].

A fantastic class of hash works with specific properties that qualify it for use in cryptography is the cryptographic hash work. It is a number that transforms sensitive data into a fixed-length bit string (a hash). It is expected to be a finite limit, that is, fixed. An essential part of internet data security tools are hash functions. Hashing functions that are used in a variety of security-related applications are known as cryptographic hash functions. Numerous other applications, including the creation of digital signatures and arbitrary number ages, can benefit from this feature as well. The majority of hash functions rely on the advancement of Merkle-Damgard [6].

3. Proposed Model

We suggest an improved framework that combines AES encryption, Diffie-Hellman key exchange, and SHA for data integrity with multiple innovations to overcome the shortcomings of current secure communication systems. This system uses Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC) to enhance the Diffie-Hellman key exchange. ECC lowers computational overhead, offers equivalent security with smaller key sizes, and makes the system more appropriate for resource-constrained environments. This integration improves security against potential threats posed by quantum computing while also guaranteeing efficient key exchange. AES is still used for data encryption because of its demonstrated reliability and efficiency, but its implementation is being optimized for different hardware platforms to guarantee consistent performance across devices [7]. The suggested system uses strong authentication techniques, like digital signatures and certificates, to verify the identities of communicating parties during the key exchange process in order to counter the threat of man-in-the-middle attacks. This guarantees that the keys are transferred safely and without being intercepted by nefarious parties. The system uses SHA-3, the most recent version, which provides improved security features and resistance to cryptographic attacks, to ensure data integrity. To further prevent tampering, keyed-hash message authentication codes (HMAC) are used to securely transmit the hash values. Automated key distribution and rotation protocols simplify key management by guaranteeing that encryption keys are safely stored and updated on a regular basis, reducing the possibility of key leaks [8]. With hierarchical key management architecture that effectively supports large-scale deployments, the suggested system also places a strong emphasis on scalability. Through the resolution of computational overhead, quantum vulnerability, authentication, key management, and data integrity concerns, the suggested system provides a complete and long-lasting secure communication solution that can be used for anything from private conversations to safeguarding vital infrastructure.

Compared to current systems, the suggested secure communication system with Diffie-Hellman key exchange, AES encryption, and SHA data integrity offers a number of noteworthy advantages.

3.1. Lessened Computational Overhead: The proposed system combines the Diffie-Hellman key exchange with Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC) to achieve similar security with smaller key sizes. Because of the decreased computational and storage needs resulting from the smaller

key size, the system is more effective and appropriate for devices with constrained resources, like mobile and Internet of Things devices.

3.2. Quantum Resistance: By utilizing ECC, the system becomes more resilient to potential dangers posed by quantum computing in the future. Although quantum attacks can compromise the security of conventional Diffie-Hellman and RSA algorithms, ECC offers a stronger defense against these intrusions, guaranteeing the system's resilience in the face of technological progress.

3.3 Utilizing a cloud server's Diffie-Hellman key exchange protocol

The provided diagram demonstrates how to implement secure communication using the Diffie-Hellman key exchange protocol in a cloud server environment. Here's a step-by-step breakdown of the process depicted in the diagram:

1. User Enters Server for the First Time:
 - A user accesses the cloud server for the first time, initiating the account creation process.
2. Account Creation:
 - The user provides necessary details, which are sent to the cloud server to create an account.
 - The cloud server processes the account creation and generates a unique user ID for the user.
3. User ID Sent to the User:
 - The cloud server sends the newly generated user ID back to the user. This user ID will be used for future interactions and identification.
4. Details Sent to the Cloud Server:
 - The user's details, including the user ID, are sent to the cloud server. This step likely includes authentication and verification of the user's identity.
5. Exchange of Diffie-Hellman keys
 - This starts the Diffie-Hellman key exchange protocol between the user and the cloud server. Without actually transmitting the key, this cryptographic procedure enables the user and the server to safely generate a shared secret key over an unsecure channel.

- The cloud server combines the generated key with the user ID for secure communication.

6. Connection Established:

- With the Diffie-Hellman key exchange complete, a secure connection is established between the user and the cloud server.
- This secure connection ensures that all subsequent communications are encrypted and protected against eavesdropping or tampering.

In summary, this diagram illustrates a secure account creation and connection establishment process using Diffie-Hellman key exchange to ensure data confidentiality and integrity. The cloud server plays a central role in generating user IDs, managing user details, and facilitating secure key exchange, thereby providing a secure communication framework.

Figure 2: Secure Communication Process

4. Experimental Results:

Use the Secure Hash Algorithm (SHA) in conjunction with the Diffie-Hellman key exchange to enable secure communication in Python. This code demonstrates how to use SHA to protect data integrity and how to generate a Diffie-Hellman key.

4.1 Combining SHA and the Diffie-Hellman Key Exchange

Step 1: Diffie-Hellman Key Exchange

First, let's generate the Diffie-Hellman keys for both parties.

Step 2: SHA Hashing for Data Integrity

Next, let's use the derived key to create a SHA-256 hash for ensuring data integrity.

This integrated example's user side function mimics the user's creation of a private/public key pair, public key exchange with the server, shared key derivation, and data HMAC hashing. The server side function simulates the server verifying the HMAC hash with its own derived key.

By using Diffie-Hellman key exchange and SHA for hashing, this process ensures that the communication between the user and the server is both confidential and tamper-proof.

Step 3: Integration

Here's how you can integrate the key exchange and hashing process in a secure communication scenario:

The Diffie-Hellman key and SHA code generated for the uploaded file are shown in the diagrams below. This file will undergo integrity checking using the information provided. Click the "Download Secure File" link to view and download the list of uploaded files, which looks like the screen below. This file is accessible to all authenticated users, either as senders or recipients.

Figure 3: File Uploading

Figure 4: File Integration.

5. Conclusion

In the modern landscape of digital communication, the imperative to safeguard sensitive information from unauthorized access and tampering has driven the development and integration of advanced cryptographic techniques. This paper explores the cooperative application of the Diffie-Hellman key exchange protocol, the Secure Hash Algorithm (SHA), and the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) to establish a solid foundation for secure communication. When two parties use the Diffie-Hellman key exchange protocol, they can safely generate a shared secret key over an insecure channel. Because it eliminates the need to send encryption keys directly, this shared key is essential to symmetric encryption and reduces the possibility of key interception. Once the shared secret key is established, AES, a powerful symmetric encryption algorithm, ensures data confidentiality. Its efficiency and strong security against brute-force attacks make it an ideal choice for encrypting data, ensuring that the information remains

unintelligible to unauthorized entities. Data integrity and authenticity are vitally important for SHA functions to further strengthen this framework for secure communication. With SHA, any unauthorized changes to the data can be detected by producing distinct hash values for each input of the data. By enabling the recipient to confirm the accuracy and legitimacy of the data they have received, this protects against manipulation and guarantees reliability. The integration of Diffie-Hellman, AES, and SHA addresses the three pillars of secure communication: confidentiality, integrity, and authenticity. This thorough approach guarantees that the data has not been altered during transmission and that the communicating parties are authentic in addition to encrypting the data to prevent unauthorized access. Through this integrated cryptographic framework, we achieve a high level of security that is robust against a wide range of attacks. The Diffie-Hellman key exchange secures the key transmission, AES ensures data confidentiality, and SHA verifies data integrity. Together, they provide a reliable and secure communication system that meets the demands of modern digital interactions. In conclusion, the amalgamation of Diffie-Hellman key exchange, AES, and SHA forms a powerful triad in the domain of secure communication. As security challenges continue to evolve, the adoption and enhancement of such integrated cryptographic solutions will remain essential in protecting the integrity and confidentiality of digital communications, ensuring that sensitive information remains secure in an increasingly interconnected world.

References:

- 1.M. Azarmipour, R. Hana, Z. Ansar and T. Kleinert, "Secure Communication between Information Technology and Operational Technology," IECON 2021 – 47th Annual Conference of the IEEE Industrial Electronics Society, Toronto, ON, Canada, 2021, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/IECON48115.2021.9589485.
2. Hadi , H. H. ., & Neamah, A. A. . (2023). Diffie-Hellman Key Exchange Based on Block Matrices Combined with Elliptic Curves. *International Journal of Intelligent Systems and Applications in Engineering*, 11(5s), 353–360. Retrieved from <https://ijisae.org/index.php/IJISAE/article/view/2799>
3. F. J. D'souza and D. Panchal, "Advanced encryption standard (AES) security enhancement using hybrid approach," *2017 International Conference on Computing, Communication and Automation (ICCCA)*, Greater Noida, India, 2017, pp. 647-652, doi: 10.1109/CCAA.2017.8229881.
4. Khan, B. U. I., Olanrewaju, R. F. ., Morshidi, M. A. ., Mir, R. N. ., Miss Laiha Binti Mat Kiah, & Khan, A. M. . (2022). EVOLUTION AND ANALYSIS OF SECURE HASH ALGORITHM (SHA) FAMILY. *Malaysian Journal of Computer Science*, 35(3), 179–200. <https://doi.org/10.22452/mjcs.vol35no3.1>

5. Samrat Mitra, Samanwita Das, Malay Kule Prevention of the Man-in-the-Middle Attack on Diffie–Hellman Key Exchange Algorithm: A Review Proceedings of International Conference on Frontiers in Computing and Systems, 2021, Volume 1255 ISBN : 978-981-15-7833-5.
6. Malviya, I., & Chetty, T. (2019). Performance and Limitation Review of Secure Hash Function Algorithm. *International Journal on Recent and Innovation Trends in Computing and Communication*, 7(6), 48–51. <https://doi.org/10.17762/ijritcc.v7i6.5323>.
7. N. Mehibel and M. Hamadouche, "A new approach of elliptic curve Diffie-Hellman key exchange," *2017 5th International Conference on Electrical Engineering - Boumerdes (ICEE-B)*, Boumerdes, Algeria, 2017, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/ICEE-B.2017.8192159.
8. H. E. Michail, A. P. Kakarountas, A. Milidonis and C. E. Goutis, "Efficient implementation of the keyed-hash message authentication code (HMAC) using the SHA-1 hash function," *Proceedings of the 2004 11th IEEE International Conference on Electronics, Circuits and Systems, 2004. ICECS 2004.*, Tel Aviv, Israel, 2004, pp. 567-570, doi: 10.1109/ICECS.2004.1399744.